

CAN THE DE BROGLIE RELATION BE MODIFIED FOR ACCOMMODATING RELATIVISTIC CORRECTIONS IN THE SCHRÖDINGER EQUATION?

ABSTRACT

The main objective of the present paper is to investigate on the de Broglie relation and determine its consequences on the time-independent Schrödinger equation, and whether the results are actually valid in terms of accommodating relativistic modifications in the Schrödinger equation. The de Broglie relation has been modified by considering the relativistic equation for energy. The goal is not to reach at a particular result. Rather, some known equations are manipulated to produce a general result which is compared to the conventional results.

INTRODUCTION TO THE DE BROGLIE EQUATION

The de Broglie relation, for the first time, introduced the idea of wave-particle duality in physics.

Max Planck proved, in the early twentieth century, that energy cannot radiate randomly and continuously; but in discrete packets called quanta (singular: quantum). The energy of each quantum is given by the equation:

$$E = hf \quad (1)$$

where $h = 6.62607004 \times 10^{-34} \text{ m}^2\text{kg/s}$ (Planck constant); f is the frequency of the radiation. (This formula holds for light, too. Light can be assumed to be a stream of particles called photons, each with an energy hf . The particle nature of light could explain many phenomena (like photoelectric effect), which the wave theory could not explain. However, the wave theory of light was also successful in explaining certain phenomena like interference, diffraction etc.. Thus, in modern physics, light is treated as having both a particle nature as well as a wave nature.)

De Broglie equated the above equation with the rest mass energy:

$$E = mc^2 \quad (2)$$

In the case of light (that is, photons), this gives $\frac{h}{p} = \lambda$, where $p = mv$ is the linear momentum of the particle, which is the mass multiplied by the velocity. (In the derivation, the case of light was considered. And for the case of light, $p = mc$, where c is the speed of light in vacuum (299792458 m/s).) λ represents the wavelength of light. The velocity of a wave v is given by:

$$v = f\lambda \quad (3)$$

where f represents the frequency of the wave; λ represents the wavelength. (For the case of light, $c = f\lambda$.)

Thus, the de Broglie relation is:

$$\frac{h}{p} = \lambda \quad (4)$$

In general, any particle must exhibit wave-particle duality. The wave nature of particles will be felt when the probe into the particle is over regions comparable to the wavelength associated with the particle. For daily-life macroscopic objects, the wavelength is negligibly small to give rise to any perceptible wavelike phenomena.

According to relativistic mechanics, the mass-energy-momentum relation is given by:

$$E^2 = m^2c^4 + p^2c^2 \quad (5)$$

where E is energy, m is mass (more specifically, the rest mass), p is relativistic momentum, c is the speed of light in vacuum. Here, $p = \gamma mv$, where the Lorentz factor γ is given by:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (6)$$

Here, v is the velocity of the object. γm is the relativistic mass.

For objects at rest, $p = 0$; and the energy E is given by mc^2 . For objects that have no rest mass (like light, that is, photons), $m = 0$; and the energy is given by pc . For light waves, $c = f\lambda$. Thus, $E = p f \lambda$. Equating this with hf , we get the de Broglie equation: $\frac{h}{p} = \lambda$.

INTRODUCTION TO THE TIME-INDEPENDENT SCHRÖDINGER EQUATION

After de Broglie proposed the wave nature of matter, many physicists, including Schrödinger, explored the consequences. The idea quickly emerged that, because of its wave character, a particle's trajectory and destination cannot be precisely predicted for each particle individually. However, each particle goes to a definite place. After compiling enough data, one gets a distribution related to the particle's wavelength and diffraction pattern. There is a certain probability of finding the particle at a given location, and the overall pattern is called a probability distribution.

Schrödinger developed an equation that gave the solution to the wave-function of a particle. The wave-function (denoted by the Greek letter Ψ) is a mathematical function, which has no physical significance by itself. The square of the wave-function, that is, the product of Ψ and its complex conjugate Ψ^* , gives the probability of finding the particle in a given region of space.

The wave-function can be expressed as:

$$\Psi = A + iB \quad (7)$$

where A and B are real functions; $i = \sqrt{-1}$ is the imaginary number.

The complex conjugate Ψ^* of Ψ is given by: $\Psi^* = A - iB$

The square of the wave-function: $|\Psi|^2 = \Psi \cdot \Psi^* = A^2 - i^2 B^2 = A^2 + B^2$. (Since, $i^2 = -1$, $i^2 B^2 = -B^2$.)

Thus, $|\Psi|^2$ is always a positive and real quantity.

The wave-function, in general, is given by:

$$\Psi = Ae^{i(kx - \omega t)} \quad (8)$$

in one-dimension. Here, A represents the amplitude of the wave; e is Euler's number, 2.71828; $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$; $\omega = 2\pi f$ (angular frequency).

The time-independent Schrödinger equation is:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \Psi + U\Psi = E\Psi \quad (9)$$

where $\hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi}$ is the reduced Planck's constant; m represents the mass of the particle; $\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2}$ is the Laplacian operator (which describes the wave-function (or any other function) in three-dimensions); U is the potential energy of the particle. The E on the Right Hand Side of equation (9) represents the total energy. The equation basically states that the Hamiltonian operator operated on the wave-function gives energy as a result, that is, $E\Psi = \hat{H}\Psi$. Here, $\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 + U\right]$ is the Hamiltonian operator, \hat{H} .

USING $E^2 = m^2c^4 + p^2c^2$ IN THE DE BROGLIE EQUATION

If the equation $E^2 = (mc^2)^2 + (pc)^2$ is used to find a relation in terms of h , p and λ , the result turns out to be different.

$$E = \sqrt{m^2c^4 + p^2c^2}$$

Using $E = hf$,

$$hf = \sqrt{m^2c^4 + p^2c^2}$$

$$hf = \sqrt{m^2c^4 + (\gamma mv)^2c^2}$$

(Here, γm is the relativistic mass, where γ is $\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$ and m is the rest mass.)

$$hf = \sqrt{m^2c^4 + \gamma^2 m^2 v^2 c^2}$$

$$hf = \sqrt{m^2c^2(c^2 + \gamma^2 v^2)}$$

$$hf = mc\sqrt{(c^2 + \gamma^2 v^2)}$$

Multiplying both sides by γv ,

$$\gamma h v f = \gamma m v c \sqrt{(c^2 + \gamma^2 v^2)}$$

Using $v = f\lambda$, and $p = \gamma mv$,

$$\gamma h f^2 \lambda = p c \sqrt{(c^2 + \gamma^2 v^2)}$$

Squaring both sides,

$$\frac{\gamma^2 h^2}{p^2 c^2} = \frac{c^2 + \gamma^2 v^2}{f^4 \lambda^2}$$

$$\frac{\gamma^2 h^2}{p^2 c^2} = \frac{c^2}{f^4 \lambda^2} + \frac{\gamma^2 v^2}{f^4 \lambda^2}$$

$$\frac{\gamma^2 h^2}{p^2 c^2} = \frac{c^2}{(f\lambda)^2 f^2} + \frac{\gamma^2 v^2}{(f\lambda)^2 f^2}$$

Using $v = f\lambda$,

$$\frac{\gamma^2 h^2}{p^2 c^2} = \frac{c^2}{v^2 f^2} + \frac{\gamma^2 v^2}{v^2 f^2}$$

Using $\frac{v}{f} = \lambda$,

$$\frac{\gamma^2 h^2}{p^2 c^2} = \frac{c^2}{v^2 f^2} + \frac{\gamma^2 \lambda^2}{v^2}$$

Using $f = \frac{v}{\lambda}$,

$$\frac{\gamma^2 h^2}{p^2} = c^2 \left(\frac{c^2 \lambda^2}{v^4} + \frac{\gamma^2 \lambda^2}{v^2} \right)$$

$$\frac{\gamma^2 h^2}{p^2} = \frac{c^4 \lambda^2}{v^4} + \frac{\gamma^2 c^2 \lambda^2}{v^2}$$

$$\frac{\gamma^2 h^2}{p^2} = \lambda^2 \left(\frac{c^4}{v^4} + \frac{\gamma^2 c^2}{v^2} \right)$$

$$\frac{h}{p} = \lambda \left(\sqrt{\frac{c^4 + c^2 v^2 \gamma^2}{\gamma^2 v^4}} \right) \quad (10)$$

The result of $\frac{h}{p}$ is λ multiplied by a constant, say, $\sqrt{\zeta} = \left(\sqrt{\frac{c^4 + c^2 v^2 \gamma^2}{\gamma^2 v^4}} \right)$. Thus, $\zeta = \frac{c^4 + c^2 v^2 \gamma^2}{\gamma^2 v^4}$ (11)

This expression may be simplified as follows:

$$\zeta = \frac{c^4 + c^2 v^2 \gamma^2}{\gamma^2 v^4}$$

$$\zeta = \frac{c^4}{\gamma^2 v^4} + \frac{c^2 v^2 \gamma^2}{\gamma^2 v^4} = \frac{c^4}{\gamma^2 v^4} + \frac{c^2}{v^2}$$

$$\zeta = \frac{c^4}{\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \right)^2} + \frac{c^2}{v^2}$$

$$\zeta = \frac{c^4}{\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{c^2 - v^2}{c^2}}} \right)^2} + \frac{c^2}{v^2}$$

$$\zeta = \frac{c^4}{\left(\frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}} \right)^2} + \frac{c^2}{v^2}$$

$$\zeta = \frac{c^4}{\frac{c^2 v^4}{(c^2 - v^2)}} + \frac{c^2}{v^2}$$

$$\zeta = \frac{c^4 (c^2 - v^2)}{c^2 v^4} + \frac{c^2}{v^2}$$

$$\zeta = \frac{c^2(c^2 - v^2)}{v^4} + \frac{c^2}{v^2}$$

$$\zeta = \frac{c^4 - c^2v^2}{v^4} + \frac{c^2}{v^2}$$

$$\zeta = \frac{c^4 - c^2v^2 + c^2v^2}{v^4} = \frac{c^4}{v^4}$$

$$\zeta = \frac{c^4}{v^4} \quad (12)$$

Thus, the result is

$$\frac{h}{p} = \lambda\sqrt{\zeta} = \lambda\sqrt{\frac{c^4}{v^4}} = \frac{\lambda c^2}{v^2} \quad (13)$$

(It should be noted that the modified equation is still dimensionally correct, as the original equation. This is because the dimension of both v and c is the same (both being metres per second, that is, velocity). Thus, the constant ζ , being $\frac{c^4}{v^4}$, is dimensionless.)

This expression collapses to $\frac{h}{p} = \lambda$ only at $v = c$. This makes sense, since in the original derivation of the de Broglie relation, the assumption was that $v = c$. At $v = 0$, however, this expression goes undefined. That is acceptable, since at $v = 0$, the momentum p also becomes zero.

MODIFICATIONS ON THE SCHRÖDINGER EQUATION BASED ON THE ABOVE RESULT

In the derivation of the time-independent Schrödinger equation, the wave-function is taken to be:

$$\Psi(x) = A \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}x\right) \quad (14)$$

Taking the second-order derivative of the wave-function, Ψ ,

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2}\Psi(x) = -\frac{4\pi^2}{\lambda^2}\Psi(x) = -\frac{4\pi^2 p^2 \zeta}{h^2}\Psi(x) \quad (15)$$

($\Psi(x)$ indicates that the wave-function is one-dimensional (x -dimension). For convenience, we may also express this as just Ψ .)

Let the total energy be E and potential energy be U . The relativistic kinetic energy is given by:

$$(\gamma - 1)mc^2 \quad (16)$$

where $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$; m is rest mass and c is the speed of light in vacuum.

(This is because, in relativity, the total energy is given by γmc^2 , which must be the sum of the kinetic and potential energies. The potential energy is the same as the rest-mass energy mc^2 , that is, when the body is at rest (no kinetic energy). Thus, the kinetic energy would be $\gamma mc^2 - mc^2 = (\gamma - 1)mc^2$.)

$$E = (\gamma - 1)mc^2 + U \quad (17)$$

Manipulating equation (17),

$$E = \frac{p^2}{2m} \frac{(2m)(\gamma - 1)mc^2}{p^2} + U = \frac{p^2}{2m} z + U$$

where $z = \frac{(2m)(\gamma - 1)mc^2}{p^2}$; m is the rest mass, c is the speed of light in vacuum, p is the linear momentum and γ is the Lorentz factor $\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$.

(The kinetic energy is expressed as the product of some term with $\frac{p^2}{2m}$, since $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ is the kinetic energy in classical mechanics. (The Schrödinger equation does not take into account relativistic modifications, and is classical in nature.) This will make it more convenient to determine the consequences of using the modified de Broglie equation in the Schrödinger equation.)

$$E = \frac{p^2}{2m} z + \frac{2m}{2m} U = \frac{p^2 z + 2mU}{2m}$$

$$2mE = p^2 z + 2mU$$

$$2mE - 2mU = p^2 z$$

$$\frac{2m(E - U)}{z} = p^2$$

$$\text{Using } z = \frac{(2m)(\gamma - 1)mc^2}{p^2},$$

$$p^2 = \frac{p^2(E - U)}{(\gamma - 1)mc^2} \quad (18)$$

This is obvious, since $E - U = (\gamma - 1)mc^2$ (both represent the kinetic energy).

Using $p = \gamma mv$,

$$p^2 = \frac{\gamma^2 m^2 v^2 (E - U)}{(\gamma - 1)mc^2} = \frac{\gamma^2 m v^2 (E - U)}{(\gamma - 1)c^2} \quad (19)$$

Putting this value of p^2 in equation (15),

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} \psi = - \frac{4\pi^2 \gamma^2 m v^2 (E - U) \zeta}{h^2 (\gamma - 1) c^2} \psi$$

$$\text{Using } \hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi},$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} \psi = - \frac{\gamma^2 m v^2 \zeta (E - U)}{\hbar^2 (\gamma - 1) c^2} \psi$$

$$\text{Using } \zeta = \frac{c^4}{v^4},$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} \psi = - \frac{\gamma^2 m v^2 c^4 (E - U)}{\hbar^2 v^4 (\gamma - 1) c^2} \psi = - \frac{\gamma^2 m c^2 (E - U)}{\hbar^2 v^2 (\gamma - 1)} \psi$$

$$\text{Using } \gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}},$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} \Psi = -\frac{c^2}{(c^2 - v^2)} \frac{mc^2(E - U)}{\hbar^2 v^2 (\gamma - 1)} \Psi$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} \Psi = -\frac{mc^4(E - U)}{\hbar^2 v^2 (\gamma - 1)(c^2 - v^2)} \Psi$$

Thus,

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} \Psi(x) + \frac{mc^4}{\hbar^2 v^2 (\gamma - 1)(c^2 - v^2)} (E - U) \Psi(x) = 0 \quad (20)$$

In three dimensions, this can be expressed as

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \Psi(x, y, z) + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \Psi(x, y, z) + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \Psi(x, y, z) + \frac{mc^4}{\hbar^2 v^2 (\gamma - 1)(c^2 - v^2)} (E - U) \Psi(x, y, z) = 0 \quad (21)$$

(For convenience, $\Psi(x, y, z)$ can be expressed as just Ψ .)

$$\nabla^2 \Psi + \frac{mc^4(E - U)}{\hbar^2 v^2 (\gamma - 1)(c^2 - v^2)} \Psi = 0$$

$$-\nabla^2 \Psi = \frac{mc^4(E - U)}{\hbar^2 v^2 (\gamma - 1)(c^2 - v^2)} \Psi$$

$$-\frac{\hbar^2 v^2 (\gamma - 1)(c^2 - v^2)}{mc^4} \nabla^2 \Psi = (E - U) \Psi$$

$$-\frac{\hbar^2 v^2 (\gamma - 1)(c^2 - v^2)}{mc^4} \nabla^2 \Psi = E \Psi - U \Psi$$

$$E \Psi = -\frac{\hbar^2 v^2 (\gamma - 1)(c^2 - v^2)}{mc^4} \nabla^2 \Psi + U \Psi$$

$$E \Psi = \left[-\frac{\hbar^2 v^2 (\gamma - 1)(c^2 - v^2)}{mc^4} \nabla^2 + U \right] \Psi \quad (22)$$

Here, our Hamiltonian is:

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2 v^2 (\gamma - 1)(c^2 - v^2)}{mc^4} \nabla^2 + U \right] \quad (23)$$

The original Hamiltonian $\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + U \right]$ of the time-independent Schrödinger equation has, thus, been modified by multiplying the first term with: $\frac{2v^2(\gamma-1)(c^2-v^2)}{c^4}$ (24). It should be noted that this extra term is dimensionless. (This is because the dimension of $c^2 - v^2$ is just the square of metres per second, which when multiplied with the v^2 in the numerator, becomes (metres/second) raised to the fourth power. This cancels out the c^4 in the denominator. The γ in the numerator is dimensionless.) Thus, the modified equation remains dimensionally correct, like the original equation.

In terms of ζ , this can also be written as:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2(\gamma-1)(c^2-v^2)}{\sqrt{\zeta}mc^2} \nabla^2 \Psi + U \Psi = E \Psi \quad (25)$$

At $v = 0$, the first term of the Left Hand Side of the equation becomes zero. (This is because $\gamma = 1$, at $v = 0$; and in this case, the term $(\gamma - 1)$ in the numerator becomes zero.)

At $v = c$, the first term of the Left Hand Side goes undefined. (This is because γ is undefined at $v = c$.)

USING RELATIVISTIC KINETIC ENERGY IN THE SCHRÖDINGER EQUATION

If the standard de Broglie relation was used in the derivation of the Schrödinger equation; but the kinetic energy was assumed to be $(\gamma - 1)mc^2$, the result would have been:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2 c^2 (\gamma - 1)}{\gamma^2 m v^2} \nabla^2 \Psi + U \Psi = E \Psi \quad (26)$$

In this case, the Hamiltonian is:

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2 c^2 (\gamma - 1)}{\gamma^2 m v^2} \nabla^2 + U \right] \quad (27)$$

The original Hamiltonian is modified by multiplying the first term with: $\frac{2c^2(\gamma-1)}{\gamma^2 v^2}$ (28)

This expression is undefined both at $v = 0$ and at $v = c$.

DISCUSSION

The results obtained by modifying the de Broglie equation are actually based on a slightly incorrect assumption. It must be noted that light is a form of electromagnetic radiation. Light does not have any rest mass. Putting $m = 0$, in the equation $E^2 = m^2 c^4 + p^2 c^2$, the result obtained is $E = pc$. Equating this with hf directly produces the de Broglie equation $\frac{h}{p} = \lambda$. This equation relates a particle's wave nature with its particle nature. The equation is mostly applied to photons and electrons; and in both of these cases, $\frac{h}{p} = \lambda$ works just fine. If the energy was assumed to be γmc^2 instead of mc^2 , the result would have been:

$$\lambda = \frac{h}{\gamma m v} \quad (29)$$

Thus, it is clear that equating hf with $\sqrt{m^2 c^4 + p^2 c^2}$ is, though tempting, actually incorrect while dealing with any kind of radiation (like electromagnetic radiation or light). However, the results obtained might be useful in certain circumstances, when, for instance, radiation can be approximated as a stream of particles with significant rest mass, as well as significant velocity. The results derived offer scope for further investigation.

The calculation on the time-independent Schrödinger equation is, again, of no direct practical importance. This approach is not valid, when it comes to accommodating relativistic corrections in the Schrödinger equation. Though the Schrödinger equation is classical, it produces good-enough results in most cases. The formal approach taken in uniting special relativity with quantum mechanics is different. The relation between mass, energy and momentum in special theory of relativity can be used in quantum mechanics. The corresponding equations are given by the Klein-Gordon equation and the Dirac equation, instead of the Schrödinger equation.

The Klein-Gordon equation can be derived from the formula: $E^2 = m^2 c^4 + p^2 c^2$. In place of E and p , one can put the Energy and momentum operators, respectively, to derive the Klein-Gordon equation. The energy operator is given by $\hat{E} = -\frac{\hbar}{i} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$; and the momentum operator is given by $\hat{p} =$

$\frac{\hbar}{i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x}$. Using these results in $E^2 = m^2c^4 + p^2c^2$, we get $-\hbar^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} = m^2c^4 - c^2\hbar^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}$. On simplification, this gives the Klein-Gordon equation:

$$\left[\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{m^2c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] \Psi = 0 \quad (30)$$

However, the Klein-Gordon equation fails to account for the property of spin. Thus, the Klein-Gordon equation was modified into the Dirac equation.

CONCLUSION

It can be satisfactorily concluded the de Broglie relation works really well for the cases it is meant for. The results obtained in this paper are of limited practical application. However, the results can be investigated further for certain cases, where that might produce more accurate results than the standard equations.